

Dissemination and Communication Strategy – **updated** – 2019.04

- with results of year 3 (April 2018 – April 2019)

Grant Agreement no.: 642025

Funded through: EU-Commission, H2020, Societal Challenge 5, "Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials"

Instrument: Coordination & Support Action

Start date of Project: 01 February 2015

End date of Project: 31 July 2020

Duration: 66 months

Deliverable no.: D2.1

Delivery name: Dissemination and Communication Plan

Deliverable update due: April 2019 (Mn51)

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Total no. of pages (incl. cover page): 36

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1205498

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 642025

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1. Foreword

This document intends to provide an update to the Dissemination and Communication Strategy. The structure of the document has not changed. The main parts of the previous contents are still present, but no deviations have been taking into account on the basis of the feedback received last year.

NCPs CaRE is in the maturity phase and concerning the communication it can be considered well positioned among the NCPs and applicants communities.

For this reason no additional actions should be taken into account for the next period. Based on the above: **It's sufficient to implement the communication and the dissemination activities maintaining constant the current level.**

2. Introduction

The experience and the daily work encourage the development of an effective conceptual framework for communication and dissemination.

Due to the need of communicating and disseminating to different types of target groups, a structured **Communication and Dissemination Strategy** has been designed in order to ensure a wider communication of the NCPs CaRE mission, and disseminate its results and activities among the Beneficiaries (and also Partner Organisations), as well as among the target audiences of the network.

Dissemination is linked only to the results of the project. These are often disseminated within the action's own community (e.g. presentation at scientific conferences, a peer reviewed publication). Promoting the action and its results on the other hand goes beyond that, as it means taking strategic and targeted measures for **communicating** (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

The plan will have a double function:

- a. The **dissemination section** will optimise the visibility of the project's results: a spectrum of proper dissemination channels will be used and adapted to the targeted groups.
- b. The **section** dedicated to **communication** will define the communication goals, target audiences, main messages to be conveyed and the strategy to be adopted to overcome the barriers that could negatively affect the communication of NCPs CaRE and improve the engagement of the primary and the secondary target about the activities of the project.

Both channels and groups will be listed in this **Dissemination and Communication Strategy**.

2.1 Project's positioning

National Contact Points (NCPs) perform valuable services in guiding and supporting national applicants in preparing proposals for Horizon 2020 funding. We expect that through an enhanced cooperation and networking between these national entities, a higher quality of their consulting services and thus of proposals and projects can be achieved.

Therefore, the **overall objective of NCPs CaRE** is to form a joint cooperation network of experienced and less-experienced NCPs on Societal Challenge 5 (SC5) "Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials" which aims at pooling their resources and know-how to raise the overall quality of services provided to their clients. By involving 23 formally nominated National Contact Points across Europe, the NCPs CaRE project will significantly strengthen transnational cooperation. In addition, NCPs CaRE will extensively involve the 26 NCPs that have decided to become a "Partner Organisation (PO)", i.e. associated partner. To harness synergies is especially relevant to SC5 NCPs, since potential applicants within this challenge are very diverse with respect to their scientific or organisational background, level of experience, involvement in transnational networks. Specifically, activities of NCPs CaRE towards this goal include, amongst others, teaming and twinning schemes, the compilation of best practices handbooks and manuals, events, meetings and trainings both on-line and on a face-to-face basis, as well as a wide range of other communication and dissemination tools and platforms. These activities foreseen by NCPs CaRE will contribute to enhance the impact of R&I in SC5. Furthermore, to ensure a more efficient use of resources and R&I developments by improving the workflow between NCPs, applicants, the European Commission (EC), and other parties with a stake in SC5. Tailor-made like they are for the SC5 clientele, these activities will make it easier for all those participating, and benefitting NCPs to enhance the number of proposals with regards to both quantity and quality.

2.2 Project's objectives

Horizon 2020 aims to exploit the potential of Europe's talent pool and ensure that the benefits of an innovation-led economy and society are maximised. The NCPs responsible for SC5 are dedicated to make their contribution towards this goal.

Therefore, the **overall objective of NCPs CaRE** is:

- To strengthen the transnational network and professional capacities of all – experienced and less-experienced – SC5 NCPs with a view to provide the European research and innovation community with the highest level of support.

The NCPs CaRE consortium together with the Partner Organisations will **aim** at:

- pooling their resources and know-how to raise the quality of services provided to their clients
- preparing carefully designed and selected activities for improving the NCPs' routines
- cooperating with important stakeholders from other advice services, policy groups and the EU Commission to work on new issues in Horizon 2020 like new applicant groups, innovation aspects or maximising impacts of projects.

In order to make the achievement of this overall objective measurable, it is broken down into seven specific objectives which are listed below.

The **specific objectives** of NCPs CaRE are to:

- I. Help newcomers and less-experienced NCPs rapidly acquire the necessary know-how to deliver adequate NCP services
- II. Raise the overall standard and professionalism of SC5 NCP services
- III. Provide potential SC5 applicants and other stakeholders with up-to-date, exhaustive and good-quality information on H2020
- IV. Help eco-innovative SMEs grasp Horizon 2020 opportunities
- V. Deliver joint and complementary activities in cooperation with relevant other networks and initiatives that have a stake in SC5 related purposes
- VI. Offer relevant partnering opportunities for potential SC5 applicants to help them build interdisciplinary and high quality collaborative projects
- VII. Ensure effective international cooperation of the NCPs and their clients, in particular with European Neighborhood Policy (ENP) countries

With regards to these specific objectives, several results (table 1) will be generated which will play a key role in the communication and dissemination activities. Indeed, the dissemination activities will aim at transferring these results towards specific target audiences, while the communication activities will have a purpose of creating engagement around these results.

Table 1 Main products and foreseen end-users of the NCPs CaRE project

Objective no	Products	End-users
I	Active SC5 NCP network	All SC5 NCPs
I,II,III	E-booklet Manual of templates & materials	All SC5 NCPs, with a focus on newcomers and ENP NCPs
II	Webinars and trainings	All SC5 NCPs
III	Website incl. communication fora	Potential applicants and stakeholders interested in SC5
IV	Dedicated SME workshops	Eco-innovative SME
V	2 workshops with another NCP Network	NCP from SC5 and from other relevant SC or LEIT
VI, VII	Matching tool	Potential SC5 applicants
IV, V, VI, VII	2 SC5 NCP Brokerage events and support to 4 EEN Brokerage events	Potential SC5 applicants

3. Dissemination and Communication objectives

The main goal of the dissemination and communication strategy is to improve the utilization of results produced during the project and to increase the brand awareness of the project. The critical element of utilization is that the project's outcome must be properly and thoroughly assimilated, and the target audience must fit the new information with her/his prior understandings and experience.

For this reason during the project, the beneficiaries will be involved in two types of activities in order to maximize the impact: dissemination and communication.

Dissemination is linked only to the results of the project which are often disseminated within the action's own community (e.g. presentation at scientific conferences, a peer reviewed publication). Promoting the action and its results on the other hand goes beyond that, as it means taking strategic and targeted measures for **communicating** about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

For this reason, the objectives will be divided into two groups: Dissemination and communication (see table 2).

Table 2 Objectives' framework

Dissemination objectives:	Communication objectives:
to maximize the impact of the project's results	to improve the brand awareness of NCPs CaRE
to transfer the project's results to a target audience	to improve the visibility of EU Commission's support
to reach the wider audience to share the tools developed by the project	to improve the visibility of activities and services offered by NCPs CaRE
	to improve and stimulate the communication flux among the NCPs Network
	to stimulate dialogue concerning common priorities and research objectives in the field of Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials
	to improve Knowledge of European opportunities (Life, JPI, ERA-NET, and other funding programmes) linked to the Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials themes
	to improve the communication process within the project among the partners especially the newcomers
	to optimise the visibility of the project's results

4. Primary and secondary target groups

The selection of primary and secondary target groups is important to describe the scope and characteristics of the "potential users" that dissemination and communication activities are designed to reach for each objective.

The **primary target** of NCPs CaRE is **represented by all SC5 NCPs and different applicants in Societal Challenge 5: climate action, environment resource efficiency, and raw materials.**

They are potentially linked to activities and services offered by NCPs CaRE and funding opportunity of Horizon 2020 – the framework programme for R&I.

Table 3 Primary target groups of NCPs CaRE

Sector	Why are they a potential target group?
SC5 NCPs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All NCPs CaRE Beneficiaries and Partner Organisations SC5 Newcomer NCPs SC5 NCPs from ENP countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interested to improve quality of services provided to their clients Interested to improve the quality of their daily work with new tool and services Interested to raise the overall standard and professionalism
Possible H2020 SC5 Applicants: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers from academia and industry sector SMEs Industries Third sector Public Sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> interested to funding opportunity promoted by NCPs CaRE interested in policies interested in tools interested in partner search interested in business opportunities interested to explore the SME Instrument (for SMEs) – now located within EIC Interested to participate to the event organised from NCPs CaRE Interested to use the tool & services developed by NCPs CaRE
EU Initiatives (i.e. EC, EIP, JPIs, KICs, ERA-NET)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two-way communication in order to explore possible joint activities

The **secondary clientele** is not of direct interest to the NCPs CaRE activities, but it could influence the primary clientele. Indeed, our secondary clientele is involved in actions to improve the performance and the participation of our primary clientele in Horizon 2020 activities.

Table 4 Secondary target groups of NCPs CaRE

Sector	Why are they a potential target group?
Other NCP networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to create joint activities
Grant Offices Third Sector (association, chambers of commerce) consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> interested in funding opportunity to share with researchers interested in policies to share with the researchers involved in the proposal writing interested in tools to do some actions more efficient than now interested in enriching their offer to clients
SC5 NCPs from third countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to share H2020 information in their countries

5. Message

The Message Framework provides a common lexicon for all to draw from and consists of words as well as phrases to describe in a consistent way. NCPs CaRE's most important characteristics across all communication medians (news and magazine articles, videos, and other university platforms).

Table 5 Message Framework

Positioning	NCPs CaRE is a network of National Contact Points for the Societal Challenge 5: Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials.
Tagline (e.g.: intro in the website or social media profile).	NCPs CaRE is a network of National Contact Points for the Societal Challenge 5: Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. The main objective is to provide the European research and innovation community with the highest level of support to improve the participation in Horizon 2020
Benefit	NCPs CaRE helps you to simplify your life in SC5 within Horizon 2020
Elevator pitch for external use	NCPs CaRE is the network of National Contact Points for the Societal Challenges 5: Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. The main objective of this project is to provide the European research and innovation community and more in general the actors involved in the Societal Challenges 5 with the highest level of support to improve the participation in Horizon 2020. NCPs CaRE helps you to find appropriate counterparts, build links, share research priorities and to establish fruitful professional connections

Besides the message framework, **two main communication messages** have been extracted to act as **guiding principles** for any specific circumstance. These messages must be clear and consistent across all kinds of communications such as leaflets, brochures and websites, but also for media interviews or conversations with your stakeholders:

1. NCPs CaRE helps you to simplify your life in SC5 within Horizon 2020
2. NCPs CaRE helps you to find appropriate counterparts, build links, share research priorities and to establish fruitful professional connections

6. Strategy

In each dissemination and communication strategy, there are highlighted some elements that could prevent the project from reaching the targeted audience or minimizing its impact. These elements are considered as barriers and the strategy (the next point) should provide certain instruments to bypass them.

In accordance with the **risk analysis** elaborated during the proposal writing phase and on the basis of the feedback collected during the project implementation, the following **possible barriers** have been identified:

- Vulnerability to vital staff being sick, and/or leaving, staff changes
- The project has a reputation to build
- Overload of information about H2020 originating from other actors
- Losing skilled NCPs (e.g. due to turnover)

The communication and dissemination strategy and plan will be task oriented. The choice and planning of activities will be chosen strategically based on the project's activity calendar and of the results and deliverables, when they are made available. The activity choice will be shared with the consortium, agreeing together how to best share and attribute responsibility.

The first challenge for the NCPs CaRE was (and is) represented by awareness-raising of the project and its mission. For this reason, it was important that especially at the beginning of the project each project partner shares the mission and the name of NCPs CaRE to a wider audience during info days, seminars and events related to Horizon 2020.

Creating engagement and interaction with the primary and secondary target group gave us the possibility to maintain a high and constant interest towards NCPs CaRE activities. For this reason, and especially at the beginning of the project, the communication activities performed through the channels described below continues to play a main role. With the first project results produced, it has been easier to setup the dissemination activities.

We can synthesize the above mentioned strategy into four main phases that describe the approach that should be followed when we meet our possible main audience (see phase 3 below) for example during training courses, events, info days or seminars:

1. Creation of a buzz among the network of each SC5 NCP to explain the mission of NCPs CaRE and to improve the brand awareness of the project.
2. Collection of the contacts interested in the project and its mission and services.
3. Establishing a constant communication and dissemination with the clients.
4. Collection of information and feedback to adapt the dissemination and communication strategy.

Figure 1 Four phases of communication strategy

This strategy was adopted especially when our target group (applicants or new NCPs) were not well aware of the mission of the project.

After setting up a “bridge” with the members of our target groups (square three in the above figure), it was important to establish a continuous flux of two way information among the partners of NCPs CaRE or from the project to the applicants.

This way the project can collect the feedback and information useful to adapt the NCPs CaRE’s dissemination and communication strategy, but also to gain the loyalty of the target groups.

To avoid confusion about the brand of NCPs CaRE, it was very important that all communication activities have a coordinated visual identity and it is essential that the project uses the same messages to share core information.

Currently, the project is well known in the SC5 community and among the SC5 NCPs. For this reason actually the strategy is focused especially on maintaining high levels of communication and dissemination activities.

Last but not least, the strategy must be flexible. The world changes rapidly and the NCPs CaRE project cannot be limited by a document.

For this reason, NCPs CaRE should be ready to evolve itself when the framework and the context change.

In order to maximize the impact of the results and materials produced by the NCPs CaRE network, NCPs CaRE maintains close collaboration with other NCP networks. Besides reciprocal sharing of information

about relevant events, NCPs CaRE regularly collects materials, articles, fact sheets etc. produced by other networks and uploads them on the NCPs CaRE website. In addition, materials produced by NCPs CaRE are shared with other NCP networks for their use and the use of their clients.

7. Dissemination and communication channels

Table 6 Use of dissemination channels

Results	Channels	Aim	Target Group
E-booklet Manual of templates & materials	Website Intranet LinkedIn Group Mailing	Share the content	SC5 NCPs
Webinars and trainings	Website Intranet	Share the materials	SC5 NCPs
Website incl. communication fora	LinkedIn Group Mailing	Share the materials	SC5 NCPs
Dedicated SME workshop	Website LinkedIn Group	Share the materials	Primary and secondary target group
2 workshops with another NCP Network	Website Intranet LinkedIn Group	Share the materials	Primary and secondary target group
Matching tool	Website Mailing	Share the results	Primary and secondary target group
2 SC5 NCP Brokerage events and support to 4 EEN Brokerage events	Website LinkedIn Group	Share the results	Primary and secondary target group

Table 7 Use of communication channels

Action	Channels	Aim	Target Group
Activation of SC5 NCP network	Website Mailing LinkedIN Group Event	Brand awareness	SC5 NCPs
Public engagement	Website Mailing LinkedIN Group Event	Brand awareness	Applicants and secondary target group
Webinars and trainings	Website Mailing	Increase the participation	SC5 NCPs
Website	Website Mailing	a. Increase participation b. share information	Primary and secondary target group
Matching tool	Website Mailing LinkedIN Group Event	Increase participation	Primary and secondary target group
Dedicated SME workshop	Website Mailing Media Event	a. Visibility of event b. increase participation	Primary and secondary target group
2 SC5 NCP Brokerage events and support to 4 EEN Brokerage events	Website Mailing Media Event	a. Visibility of event b. increase the participation	Primary and secondary target group

7.1 Visual identity and promotional material

In accordance with the strategy, a coordinated visual identity of the project has been developed to ensure consistent and recognisable communication throughout the different media. Each partner is asked to use only the dissemination material approved by the consortium. In particular:

Promotional material:

- A. A graphic template for deliverables, reports and power point presentation slides;
- B. A roll-up to be used in conferences;
- C. Flyers;
- D. Web banners to be included in partners websites' as needed;
- E. The production of other promotional items such as bags and other items will be considered case by case together with the Coordinator;
- F. For conferences, the production of additional signage items will be considered.

Figure 2 Logo

Figure 3 Document Template

Figure 4 Brochure

Figure 5 Rollup

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7.1.2 Promotional Video

For the realization of the video, the following points have been agreed upon with Task 2.2:

1. **Duration:** Up to **2 min.** movie
2. **Use:**
 - a. Presented on a screen in exhibition booths during relevant events
 - b. Introduction to presentations about NCPs CaRE during relevant events
 - c. Uploaded on the NCPs CaRE website
 - d. Any other relevant use
3. **Content:**
 - a. H2020 - ~40% of the time.
 - i. Short description – budget, duration, topics..
 - ii. Climate action in H2020 – main topics for 2014-2020
 - b. National Contact Points – ~20% of the time.
 - i. Role, how to locate your NCP
 - c. NCPs CaRE – ~40% of the time.
 - i. Benefits of a network: Partner search tool, brokerage events, etc.
4. **Visualisation:**
 - a. As the movie is to be presented at exhibitions, it has been made in such way that it can be screened with or without volume.
(Requiring mostly visual effects (graphics, etc) and English subtitles).
 - b. Filming and interviewing winning projects would have been costly and timely.
As ISERD had made several movies on success-stories for NCP projects, some key sentence/s from a successful client (SME) who benefited from contacting their local NCP were integrated.
5. URL: To watch the video go to the following link: <https://youtu.be/tfS6C3udZLc>

7.1.3 Other promotional material

Other promotional materials have been realized and will be realized to promote specific design or activity of NCPs CaRE project.

Figure 6 An example of promotional materials elaborated to promote the webinar on Life Programme

7.2 Website

The project website is a key element of dissemination and communication both during the project duration and beyond. Specifically, it is:

- ❖ a channel to create dialogue and establish a constant engagement with the primary and secondary target group;
- ❖ a dissemination and communication instrument.

It aims at improving internal communication through the realisation of an **intranet** in order to share all project reports and documents between Beneficiaries and Partner Organisation.

As for the second point, the website is accessible by the public and contains information about the project and related initiatives.

The published news are to be related to issues expressed in Societal Challenge 5: Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials and related aspects. A special focus is to be paid to International Cooperation, especially with an orientation to countries to be involved in the SC5 topics. To increase the quality of information provided by the website, a structured publication planning will be elaborated. A pilot action has been launched at the beginning of 2017 with good results in terms of visits registered in the website. This pilot action involves NCPs in charge of the development of website activities. Those NCPs have been asked to write informative news containing analysis, comments, and explanations about topics related to SC5 and relevant initiatives. The success of this initiative has suggested us to continue on this path. In specific, we will avoid writing numerous short news and instead we will focus our effort on drafting less articles but longer and more detailed.

In order to deliver broader and updated information to the public interested in European environment issues, a content aggregator has been developed and hosted on the project website in a specific section. This web tool will automatically digest the news published on the internet by different sources and websites using RSS and API technologies (including relevant R&I partnership opportunities from the EEN). The digest will serve as front-line delivery vehicle for essential insights emerging both from the environmental research and EU funding opportunity.

The website is also the repository of the dissemination material which will be made available in a downloadable format (for example, flyer, brochure and newsletter).

The website is very clear and simple in its structure. The main part of information is provided under the item “News” and “Events”, produced by different NCPs in different time-frames. Through appropriate linking, all resulting and output documents are also made available on the website. A good number of events with an orientation for SC5 has been described. During the first year of the project, certain sections not included in the original structure of the website have been developed, such as: FAQ, Other initiatives and so on. These kind of initiatives received good feedback in terms of visits and will be replicated also in the last year of the project.

Figure 7 Website homepage

Figure 8 News section

Figure 9 Socia media/Digest section

Figure 10 Event section

On the following page, there are some screenshots of the old version of the website:

7.2.1 Re-Design of the website

After two years and analyzing the performance and the feedback received for the utilization of the NCPs CaRE website, the structure of the homepage has been changed. The main objective of these changes is to provide a new user experience and friendlier utilization of the main tool and resources hosted on the web page of the project. The next screenshots will show the following:

1. The header image is changed. Random images related to SC5 appear any time a user refreshes the website.
 - The selected photos are licensed under the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. This means the pictures are allowed to be used for any legal purpose.
2. The homepage now is totally widgetable and the distribution of the news has been done on the basis of the feedback and performance. With the new layout, it is possible to reach the news, with just a click. Also the useful sections of the website are more simpler to reach and on homepage there is always a system to inform the visitors about the last updates in the different sections.
3. Less clicks are required to reach the information
4. Section "Calls" was added to the website providing up to date information on SC5 calls extracted from participant portal.
5. Section "Funding opportunities" was added to the website in order to provide user with information about opportunities for financing environmental projects (including Life, Interreg Programmes)

Screenshot of the new website design:

Figure 11 New layout of the website

7.3 External communication forum

From the beginning of 2017, the External Communication forum has been substituted with a LinkedIn group as described in the 7.8 LinkedIn group Paragraph.

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7.4 Events

In total, nine training events and two SMEs oriented workshops will be organized by the project during its life-cycle. These dissemination and communication channels will be customized on the basis of the expected target group. These activities are very important to build a new network with our main audience. Not only self-hosted events will be considered to improve the brand awareness and build a network. The NCPs involved in the NCPs CaRE where possible should promote the network and the tool and services to promote.

Indeed, it will be very important to insert our logo and present the project activities also during events organized by other actors involved in the H2020.

Minimum conditions to improve the brand awareness of NCPs CaRE is to present, where possible and in accordance with the organizers, the project at national info days linked to Societal Challenge 5 and at a main event where there is the possibility to meet our primary and secondary clientele.

7.5 Face to face activities

One important aspect of NCPs work are face to face meetings. During each meeting with potential clients, it is important to share information about the activities and results performed by NCPs CaRE.

7.6 Mailing

The mailing is the second instrument used by NCPs to communicate with the researchers, industries, SMEs and other clients interested to Horizon 2020 which are also our primary and secondary clientele. This communication channel will be another instrument to share information about the activities, results and partner search tool developed and maintained by NCPs CaRE.

To improve the internal communication and inform B and PO NCPs about the news related to NCPs CaRE, an internal mail bulletin has been created and implemented in 2016.

7.6.1 Mailing with other NCP networks

A setup of a communication channel between NCPs CaRE and relevant NCP networks has been accomplished at the beginning of the project and maintained during the implementation of the project. Emails have been chosen as the most convenient and effective communication tool. Persons responsible for communication with other NCP networks have been identified for each relevant NCP network. Contacts with them have been established and are regularly maintained, according to the needs and circumstances at hand. If necessary, also phone or skype calls take place.

Table 8 sets out relevant NCP networks and the contact details of persons responsible for cooperation with other NCPs, including their affiliation.

Table 8: Contact persons of other NCP networks

Area	NCP network	Contact person	e-mail	Organisation
SC1	HNN2.0	Buonocore Caterina	buonocore@apre.it	APRE,IT
SC2	BioHorizon	Serena Borgna	borgna@apre.it	APRE, IT
SC7	SEREN 4	Pascale van Dinter	Pascale.VANDINTER@stis.belspo.be	BELSP0
Space	COSMOS 2020	Valentina Fioroni	fioroni@apre.it	APRE, IT
NMPB	NMP TeAM4	Serena Borgna	borgna@apre.it	APRE, IT
L&F	NCP Academy	Caterina Buonocore	buonocore@apre.it	Enterprise Ireland
SC3	C-Energy 2020	Chiara Pocaterra	pocaterra@apre.it	APRE, IT
SC6	Net4Society	Natalia Morazzo	morazzo@apre.it	APRE, IT
SME Instrument	Access4SMEs	Antonio Carbone	carbone@apre.it	APRE, IT
EURATOM	NUCL-EU 2020	Bruno Mourenza	mourenza@apre.it	APRE, IT
Research Infrastructures	RICH	Daniele Gizzi	gizzi@apre.it	APRE, IT

7.7 Media

This refers to sharing news and press releases with general media, especially those present in the internet. Engaging these actors gives us the possibility to reach a wider audience.

7.8 LinkedIn Group

Considering the increased use of the social media in a globalized world and taking into consideration our target audience, a new communication channel has been setup-the NCPs CaRE LinkedIn group, which complements the internal communication section of Task 2.3 with an external dimension. NCPs have the chance to discuss all kinds of themes and activities there with various target groups (EU RI community (industry, policy makers, RFOs et al), potential H2020 SC5 applicants, relevant EU initiatives and other interested parties, such as JPIs, ETPs, relevant ERA-NETs as well as the EC global contacts and the general

public), and also to highlight opportunities for interlinkage and collaboration. Beyond that, the community may contact several NCPs at once. NCPs, on the other hand, may join efforts in counselling the community.

The LinkedIn group has been established as a communication forum and provides an attractive environment as well as a discussion forum for all target groups to respond rapidly to societal needs, policy issues and opportunities for collaboration in international research programmes.

MIZŠ is the LinkedIn group owner and has control over membership, monitors conversations and controls the rules. In May 2015, the NCPs CaRE LinkedIn group was created, publishing the first post in July 2015. MIZŠ publishes posts related to the environment topics, H2020 and wider (Cohesion policy) as well as monitors and promotes posts published from other participants in the group. In addition, MIZŠ will regularly signpost published articles from NCPs CaRE website by writing short teaser text/header and posting the link to the articles. Indicators of a functional group would be the increased number of its participants and the number of shared/likes of each posts.

MIZŠ will follow and monitor the activity of LinkedIn group and report to WP2 Leader. FORTH and MIZŠ will maintain content-wise the LinkedIn group, adjust it to the (dissemination) needs of NCPs CaRE and inform the NCPs as well as the community about it and the functions it has to offer. MIZŠ, FORTH and RANNIS will disseminate information aiming at the greater public.

FORTH will also disseminate information on partner searches, information days, brokerage events, new calls, important information and developments for H2020 that may come from different sources such as EC, EIT, EIPs, ERA-NETs, ETPs, PPPs, JTIs, Regional Agencies, as well as international cooperation projects (partner searches).

The possibility of having the website and the Partner Search Tool of Task 5.1 linked to LinkedIn should also be investigated, so that new posts are automatically uploaded on the LinkedIn group. The LinkedIn group aims to direct all group members to the website and thus increase its visits and views.

The Task Leader will also animate and interact with the community, especially of SC5 NCPs, that will follow the group activities. FORTH (& RANNIS) will assist the Task Leader in the implementation of this task.

8. Guideline for the new comers

A very important dimension of NCPs CaRE is represented by Internal Communication. Sharing the information among the NCPs is and was essential to reach the project objective. However the high level of colleagues' turnover registered in the last years has been a challenge because often the new NCPs do not fully substitute the previous ones in terms of knowledge and experience.

For this reason, to foster the internal communication between the colleagues already integrated in the NCPs CaRE and the new comers a Guide containing practical and operative information has been elaborated and placed on the NCPs CaRE website. A new update of the Guide for Newcomers has been published in April 2019 taking into account the extension of the NCPs CaRE project.

1. How to get in touch with/receive contact details of all beneficiaries of the NCPs CaRE project?
How to get access to other relevant organizations cooperating with NCPs CaRE?

There are in total 23 Beneficiaries (B) of the NCPs CaRE project. You can find the list of the beneficiaries along with a short description of their organisations, links to their websites and relevant contact details on the NCPs CaRE website, in the 'Partners' section available at: http://www.ncps-care.eu/?page_id=48.

There are 26 Partner (associated) Organisations (PO). You can find information about the names of those organizations and their countries also on the NCPs CaRE website, in the 'Partners' section. Please note that no contact details are provided in the case of associated organisations: if you would like to get in touch with them, you would need to contact the coordinator or search their contact details in the Participant Portal (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/national_contact_points.htm).

Figure 12 Guide for Newcomers to NCPs CaRE

9. Feedback

The success of the NCPs CaRE project dissemination and communication efforts is evaluated through an iterative process. It is necessary to consider the effect that the dissemination strategies have on conveying our message to end-users. Dissemination and communication is not a one-time activity, rather, it is a long-term relationship with users that will provide ongoing feedback to help us to improve our message. Some instruments will be developed to measure the results and collect the feedback from the target audience:

1. A form in the website to collect open comment from our clients about needs and barriers identified in NCPs CaRE website. It will be collected periodically in order to think of possible solutions.
2. A excel file to collect the events where NCPs CaRE will appear and the number of people potentially reached
3. Statistical analytics of the website: incl. visit, keywords, unique access, time used on the page.
4. A feedback form to evaluate the performance for each training activities organized by NCPs CaRE.

A feedback form has been developed and available at the following link: <http://bit.ly/ncpscure>

10. Monitoring, reporting and evaluation

A monitoring system has been implemented in order to have a real-time overview about the performance of the dissemination activities performed from the NCPs CaRE Project.

Following the results reached during the second period of the project

❖ Website

Time: 11/09/2017 - 03/31/2019

Visits: 771,600

Visitors: 184,112

Top Pages:

1 - Home, Visits: 141,463

2 - Register - Login, Visits: 76,668

3 - About NCPs CaRE, Visits: 3,796

4 - Useful guides, Visits: 3,169

5 - Short News from EU, Visits: 2,645

6 - Horizon 2020 - Work Programme 2018-2020: Topics for Circular Economy, Visits: 2,436

7 - Annotated proposal template SME Instrument Phase 1 and Phase 2, Visits: 2,167

8 - Partners, Visits: 1,899

9 - Events, Visits: 1,827

10 - Objectives, Visits: 1,809

Top Referring Sites:

1 - www.google.com, References: 4,805

2 - partnersearch.ncps-care.eu, References: 1,121

3 - m.facebook.com, References: 782

4 - www.google.es, References: 459

- 5 - www.google.it, References: 458
- 6 - www.google.fr, References: 369
- 7 - www.google.com.br, References: 313
- 8 - www.baidu.com, References: 313
- 9 - www.google.de, References: 297
- 10 - www.google.co.uk, References: 284

❖ **Linkedin Group**

- The groups counts 198 members with 204 followers

❖ **Events**

- **33 events where the NCPs CaRE logo appeared in year 4 Feb-2018 - Jun 2019 compared to 63 events in year 3 (see annex I)**

❖ **Newsletter (see figure 12)**

- **357 subscribers in the newsletter**
- **222 Newsletters sent**

Figure 12 Newsletter screenshot

11. ANNEX I: Events where NCPs CaRE was represented from project start up to now

Title of event	Date (sorted by dd/mm/yyyy)	Country	Partner involved
YEAR 1	April 2015 – April 2016		
Info day for industry about H2020	07.05.2015	Serbia	MIZŠ
EEN SGE meeting	12.-13.05.2015	Greece	BEA, FORTH
Conference 'Estarrreja 2020: Green growth a global commitment at a local level'	21.05.2015	Portugal	FCT
E ² Tech4Cities (EEN SGE brokerage event)	18.06.2015	Belgium	BEA, FORTH, LUXINNOVATION
Climate Information Event	25.06.2015	Switzerland	Euresearch
H2020 Opportunities for financing in 2016-2017- Efficient management of the environmental, agricultural and marine resources	18.09.2015	Portugal	FCT
Infoday 'Horizon 2020 info day in Minsk'	21.09.2015	Belarus	ETAg
Horizon 2020: Zweite Ausschreibungsrunde	22.09.2015	Austria	FFG
Infoday 'Horizon 2020 Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials info event'	29.09.2015	Switzerland	Euresearch
Horizon 2020 infoday	30.09.2015	Estonia	ETAg
Climate Action, Environment, Energy Efficiency and Raw Materials: Giornata Nazionale di Lancio dei Bandi 2016-17 in Horizon 2020	02.10.2015	Italy	APRE
Infoday 'Horizon 2020 Day-Your Roadmap to Success'	02.10.2015	Luxembourg	Luxinnovation
Horizon 2020 Information Days (IncoNet EaP)	05.10.2015	Ukraine	Juelich
National Information Day „Horizon 2020, opportunities in: Food security, sustainable agriculture, marine research and the bio-economy and Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials“	08.10.2015	Czech Republic	ASCR
H2020 Info Day	09.10.2015	Slovenia	MIZŠ
GREEK SC5 INFO DAY	12.10.2015	Greece	PRAXI Network/FORTH
HORIZON 2020 - How to Write a Good R&I Proposal	14.10.2015	Israel	ISERD
German SC5 National Info Day	15.10.2015	Germany	Juelich
Water for Health: EU- India STI Cooperation Days 2015	15.10.2015	Italy	APRE
Infoday 'Bringing Israel's Water Innovation to the EU'	15.10.2015	Israel	ISERD

National InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017	16.10.2015	Spain	CDTI
2015 EPA Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 5 National Information Day	21.10.2015	Ireland	EPA
Information day for SC5 and SC2	27.10.2015	Slovakia	CVTI SR
H2020 Opportunities for financing in 2016-2017- Climate Services	27.10.2015	Portugal	FCT
Seminar Connect-EU: SC5 - Work Programme 2016-2017	27.10.2015	Spain	CDTI
A hands-on workshop focused on WP content and on services offered by Horizon 2020 NCPs and EEN networks	28.10.2015	Belgium	Belspo (DWTI-SIST)
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (Aragón)	29.10.2015	Spain	CDTI
EEN SGE meeting – Update on NCPs CaRE activities	03.-04.11.2015	The Netherlands	BEA, EZ/RVO
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (Valencia)	10.11.2015	Spain	CDTI
Information day Focus Areas: Health, Energy, Climate and Environment (IncoNet EaP)	11.11.2015	Moldova	BEA
Social Innovation brokerage event	17.11.2015	Austria	Euresearch
Brokerage Event für das EIT RawMaterials mit dem Thema "Deep Intelligent Mining"	18.11.2015	Germany	Juelich
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (Galicia)	18.11.2015	Spain	CDTI
European Financing Mechanisms for R&D within the Energy and Environment Sector, EEA Grants	19.11.2015	Spain	CDTI
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (Andalucia)	23.11.2015	Spain	CDTI
HORIZON 2020 Raw Materials InfoDay	24.11.2015	Portugal	FCT
Horizon 2020 information meeting on Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials	26.11.2015	Sweden	VINNOVA, Formas
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (Navarra)	26.11.2015	Spain	CDTI
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (País Vasco)	30.11.2015	Spain	CDTI
Regional InfoDay SC5_Work Programme 2016-2017 (Murcia)	03.12.2015	Spain	CDTI
Info day for SC2, SC3, SC5, SPACE and NANO	07.12.2015	Slovenia	MIZŠ
H2020 Info Day	07.12.2015	Slovenia	MIZŠ
Oportunidades, desafios e perspectivas de financiamento para 2016/2017 H2020	15.12.2015	Portugal	FCT
Info Day at University of Cape Town	25.01.2016	South Africa	DST
Brokerage 'Project Ideas Laboratory. Funding Opportunities for Local Authorities'	26.01.2016	Belgium	BEA
Presentation of NCPs CaRE partner search tool	03.02.2016	Poland	IPPT

Water Match (EEN SGE brokerage event)	09.02.2016	The Netherlands	FORTH, TC ASCR
Presentation of NCPs CaRE Partner Search Tool	09.02.2016	Poland	IPPT
International Waste Management Fairs SOSEXPO 2016 Warsaw: Presentation of NCPs CaRE Partner Search Tool	17.02.2016	Poland	IPPT
Information day: Funding Opportunities for Horizon 2020 in Energy and Environment	18.02.2016	Spain	CIEMAT
AGRO Network Session	25.02.2016	Portugal	FCT
Euro - Mediterranean NCPs meeting (MEDSPRING)	04.03.2016	Belgium	RPF
23rd annual European Tyres Recycling Conference	18.03.2016	Belgium	impulse.brussels (BEA)
International ECO Technology Fairs EKOTECH 2016, Kielce: Presentation of NCPs CaRE Partner Search Tool	31.03.2016	Poland	IPPT
YEAR 2	April 2016 – April 2017		
Field trip to successful institutes in Climate Change and Health Programmes (Twinning scheme to support EaP NCP activities)	11.-13.04.2016	Italy	APRE
PIMBIS - Portugal International Mining Business & Investment Summit	12.04.2016	Portugal	FCT
What EU funding for my environmental project?	13.04.2016	Belgium	ABE
XXIII Seminar for H2020 Project Managers	20.04.2016	Spain	CDTI
Info day at Nelson Mandela Metro University	25.04.2016	South Africa	DST
EEN SGE meeting - Circular Economy: Horizon 2020 Funding Opportunities & Selected Projects / Update on NCPs CaRE activities	25.-26.04.2016	Spain	BEA, Euresearch
H2020 Info Day for Cities: Presentation of NCPs CaRE Partner Search Tool	10.05.2016	Poland	IPPT
STI DaysHanoi	11.05.2016	Vietnam	Indirectly, as presented through SEA-EU-Net II
STI Days Hanoi: NCP Training & Workshop "Climate Action and Resource Efficiency in Southeast Asia: Thematic and Funding Opportunities"	12.05.2016	Vietnam	Juelich
H2020 Info Day	01.06.2016	Slovenia	MIZŠ
Strategies and Plans to encourage R&I in Museums	06.06.2016	Spain	CDTI
Young Researchers Forum in Central Asia: Cooperation Perspectives with the European Union on Climate Change, Energy and Health in the context of Horizon 2020 (Bishkek): Presentation of NCPs CaRE Partner Search Tool	09.06.2016	Kyrgyzstan	IPPT
Oportunidades de Financiación Europea para Ciudades	10.06.2016	Spain	CDTI

Polish Wood Platform Meeting, Poznan: Presentation of NCPs CaRE Partner Search Tool	13.06.2016	Poland	IPPT
Oportunidades de Financiación para Energía y Medio Ambiente en Horizonte 2020, GENERA 2016	16.06.2016	Spain	CDTI
Ict4Water Drives Circular Economy	17.06.2016	Spain	CDTI
Calls 2017 in SC5	21.06.2016	Austria	FFG
Re-Naturing Cities: Nature Based Solution to face the Urban Challenges	23.06.2016	Spain	CDTI
CAPER-Med, Committee on Air Pollution Effects Research on Mediterranean Ecosystems	29.06.2016	Spain	CDTI
H2020 opportunities for climate adaptation in agriculture	07.07.2016	Belgium	ABE
ESOF 2016	26.07.2016	UK	APRE
Horizon 2020 Information Day & Brokerage Event "Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency & Raw Materials"	14.09.2016	Belgium (Brussels)	Nearly all NCPs CaRE partners
Info Day and brokerage event "H2020 Societal Challenge 5 2017 calls"	14.09.2016	Belgium (Brussels)	BEA, FORTH, IPPT PAN, LUXINNOVATIO, ADEME
General description of NCPs CaRE project	22.09.2016	Finland	AKA
European Researchers' Night	23.09.2016	Republic of Moldova	MRDA
ACA V Conference Serbian Ceramic Society Round table	23.09.2016	Serbia, Croatia, Germany, China, Bulgaria	Vinca Institute
Webinar on Upcoming Calls in "Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials"	27.09.2016	Switzerland	Euresearch
13th International Conference Physical Chemistry 2016 (Round table of Cost Action)	27.09.2016	Serbia (Belgrade)	Vinca Institute
Oportunidades de Financiación en Reto Social 5 de Horizonte 2020 (Foro de Ingeniería Desarrollo Sostenible de Granada)	30.09.2016	Spain	CDTI
European Researchers' Night Cyprus 2016	30.09.2016	Cyprus	RPF
Networking techniques and tools in view of EU projects	06.10.2016	Belgium	Impulse.brussels /BEA
National Infoday SC5	11.10.2016	Spain	CDTI
9th International Scientific conference "Energy and Climate Change"	14.10.2016	all over Europe	FORTH/PRAXI Network
Oportunidades en el ámbito ACCIÓN POR EL CLIMA, MEDIO AMBIENTE, EFICIENCIA DE LOS RECURSOS Y MATERIAS PRIMAS en el Programa HORIZONTE 2020: Convocatorias 2017	17.10.2016	Spain (Castilla y León)	CDTI

EEN SGE Meeting	18.–19.10.2016	United Kingdom (Edinburgh)	BEA, FCT
Oportunidades Financiación en Reto Social 5 de Horizonte 2020: Acción por el Clima, Medio Ambiente, Materias Primas y Recursos Naturales	20.10.2016	Spain	CDTI
Oportunidades Financiación Ciudades en Reto Social 5 de Horizonte 2020: Acción por el Clima, Medio Ambiente, Materias Primas y Recursos Naturales	27.10.2016	Spain	CDTI
Luonnon monimuotoisuuden tutkimuksen EU-rahoitus/H2020-haut (H2020 calls on biodiversity) incl. one slide of services of NCPs CaRE	27.10.2016	Finland	AKA
FINANCIACIÓN H2020 PARA LAS INDUSTRIAS CREATIVAS	08.11.2016	Spain	CDTI
Launch of Horizon 2020 Calls for 2017	10.11.2016	Republic of Moldova	MRDA
promotion event of joint report on 'Marine sustainability in an age of changing oceans and seas	15.-16.11.2016	Portugal (Lisbon)	FCT
InHouse Policía Municipal de Madrid	22.11.2016	Spain	CDTI
INFODAY ON H2020 SC5 2017 Call for Proposals	23.11.2016	Israel	ISERD
Infoday on Horizon 2020 SC5 2017 calls	23.11.2016	Israel	ISERD
Infoday Galicia	23.11.2016	Spain	CDTI
Horizon 2020: State of play and the way forward	29.11.2016	Slovenia	MIZŠ
OPORTUNIDADES DE FINANCIACIÓN PARA PROYECTOS DE SOSTENIBILIDAD	29.11.2016	Spain	CDTI
Info Day H2020 during POLLUTEC fair	29.11.2016	France & more	BEA
National info day	29.11.2016	International level	MIZŠ
Raw Materials Week: "Horizon 2020 Brokerage event"	30.11.2016	Belgium (Brussels)	Juelich
Info Day and brokerage event "Innovating with Nature and Culture"	08.12.2016	Belgium (Brussels)	FORTH, BEA
Infoday Navarra	13.12.2016	Spain	CDTI
Infoday Andalucía	14.12.2016	Spain	CDTI
Infoday Cataluña	16.12.2016	Spain	CDTI
Oportunidades de participación con Climate-KIC	20.12.2016	Spain	CDTI
Funding Opportunities in Societal Challenge 5	30.01.2017	Spain	CDTI
H2020 Environment & Energy Info Day	31.01.2017	Poland	IPPT PAN
International Forum of Waste Management SOSEXPO	02.02.2017	Poland	IPPT PAN
SC5 Annual Infoday	03.02.2017	Israel	ISERD

European Programmes for Cities: H2020, URBACT, Europe for Citizens, Interreg.	08.02.2017	Poland	IPPT PAN
INFODAY on H2020 SC5 2017calls	22.02.2017	Serbia	VINCA
The 6th International Conference ECOLOGICAL & ENVIRONMENTAL CHEMISTRY 2017	02.03.2017	Republic of Moldova (Chisinau)	MRDA
Horizon 2020 for Innovators	02.03.2017	Poland	IPPT PAN
Abimaterjalid Horisont 2020 keskkonnavaldkonna taotlejale	15.03.2017	Estonia	ETAg
Water Berlin + EEN SGE Meeting	27.-28.03.2017	Germany (Berlin)	EZ/RVO
H2020 Info Day at the National Technical University of Ukraine "Kyiv Polytechnic Institute" on energy and environment topics	07.04.2017	Ukraine, Poland	IPPT-PAN (EAP-Plus project)
Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking Infoday and Brokerage event	28.04.2017	Belgium (Brussels)	APRE, DWTI-STIS, BEA
YEAR 3	May 2017 – February 2018		
Berliner Energietage 2017	04.05.2017	Germany (Berlin)	Juelich
Coming H2020 SC5 calls	08.05.2017	Presentation by SKYPE	Academy of Finland & TEKES
How have Finns responded to Horizon's climate actions, raw materials, resource efficiency and environmental challenges? (in Finnish)	19.05.2017	Finland	Academy of Finland
Oportunidades de financiamento nos Desafios Societais Bioeconomia e Ação Climática em 2018-2020	20.06.2017	Portugal (Coimbra)	FCT
National Info day on BBI JU	22.06.2017	Slovakia (Bratislava)	CVTI SR
One step closer: Italian coordinators in 2 nd stage	05.07.2017	Italy (Rome)	APRE
HORIZONTE 2020: Recursos Naturais, Cidades Sustentáveis, Observação da Terra	07.07.2017	Portugal (Ponta Delgada, Azores)	FCT
Desafio Societal Ação Climática: oportunidades de financiamento na temática da economia circular e cidades sustentáveis em 2018-2020	10.07.2017	Portugal (Porto)	FCT
Horizont 2020 – Halbzeit und Ausblick - Informationsveranstaltung des EEN Berlin-Brandenburg (Berlin)	11.07.2017	Germany (Berlin)	Juelich
I risultati della partecipazione italiana ai bandi 2016-2017, buone prassi e suggerimenti per una progettazione ottimale	12.07.2017	Italy (Trieste)	APRE
Biodiversity Research and Evidence Indaba	17.08.2017	South Africa	DST

Summer school on raw materials	06.09.2017	Slovakia (Banská Štiavnica)	CVTI SR
EU Research Funding in Climate and Earth Science	14.09.2017	Germany (Hamburg)	Juelich
SC5 national info event	14.09.2017	Switzerland (Bern)	Euresearch
Infoboost at Conference and Brokerage Event "Horizon 2020 unlimited opportunities in the circular economy"	19.09.2017	Norway (Oslo)	BEA
XIII CNEA - Congresso Nacional de Engenharia do Ambiente	19.09.2017	Portugal (Lisboa)	FCT
Horizont 2020 - Fördermöglichkeiten für Forschung und Innovation in den Lebenswissenschaften	19.09.2017	Germany (Hohenheim)	Juelich
Dos and Dents for Applicants	22.09.2017	Italy (Rome)	APRE
Blue Growth: Forschungsförderung in Horizont 2020 - Arbeitsprogramm 2018-2020	26.09.2017	Germany (Hamburg)	Juelich
Waste Management expert Forum	28.09.2017	Poland (Kielce)	IPPT
Hyvän hakemuksen ainekset/The ingredients of a good application	03.10.2017	Finland (Helsinki)	EU Research and Innovation Programmes, Finland
EEN SGE Meeting	04.-05.10.2017	Italy (Rome)	BEA, FCT
CANAGUA & ENERGÍA	05.10.2017	Spain (Las Palmas de Gran Canaria)	CDTI
IFIB Brokerage Event	06.10.2017	Italy (Rome)	APRE, BEA
Fördermöglichkeiten in Horizont 2020 für den Bereich Umweltforschung und Innovation	10.10.2017	Germany (Bonn)	Juelich
CSIR- Water and waste water research group LC-CLA-05-2019a	10.10.2017	South Africa (Pretoria)	DST
National Information Day Horizon 2020, opportunities in SC2 and SC5	18.10.2017	Czech Republic (Prague)	Technology Centre CAS
POL-ECO-SYSTEM International Environmental Fair	19.10.2017	Poland (Poznan)	IPPT
Nature-based solutions: From innovation to common use	25.10.2017	Estonia (Tallinn)	Estonian Research Council
Information Session at University of Fort Hare	25.10.2017	South Africa (Alice)	DST
Portuguese Raw Materials Infoday	31.10.2017	Portugal (Lisboa)	FCT

Food Security 2017 Brokerage Event	06.11.2017	Czech Republic (Prague)	Technology Centre CAS
National Info day SC2	07.11.2017	Slovakia (Nitra)	CVTI SR
Circular Economy Brokerage event	07.11.2017	Belgium (Brussels)	BEA
HORIZON 2020 – Die Aufrufe für Projektanträge im Bereich Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Ressourceneffizienz und Rohstoffe (SC5) im Arbeitsprogramm 2018-20 (EEN Thüringen)	09.11.2017	Germany (Erfurt)	Juelich
Infobooth NCPs CaRE at SC6 Brokerage event	14.11.2017	Belgium (Brussels)	BEA
MADRID-NATIONAL INFODAY	14.11.2017	Pain (Madrid)	CDTI
H2020 opportunities for Cities	14.11.2017	Poland (Warsaw)	IPPT
H2020 SC5 and LIFE programme joint infoday	15.11.2017	Estonia (Tallinn)	ETAg
H2020 SC5 and LIFE prorgamme joint infoday	16.11.2017	Estonia (Tartu)	ETAg
CASTILLA Y LEÓN INFODAY	16.11.2017	Spain (Valladolid)	CDTI
SC5 National Information Day	16.11.2017	Slovakia (Bratislava)	CVTI SR
Launch of Horizon2020 Calls for 2018-2020	17.11.2017	Republic of Moldova	MRDA
ANDALUCÍA INFODAY	21.11.2017	Spain (Córdoba)	CDTI
Energy and Environment in H2020: Information Day	21.11.2017	Poland (Warsaw)	IPPT
GALICIA INFODAY	22.11.2017	Spain (Santiago de Compostela)	CDTI
SPACE WEEK 2017	22.11.2017	Italy (Rome)	APRE
NKS-L Symposium - Dritte Etappe in Horizont 2020 -	22.11.2017	Germany (Berlin)	Juelich
Informationstag HORIZONT 2020 & LIFE im Bereich Umwelt - Vorstellung der künftigen Themen und Beratung (EEN Baden-Württemberg)	22.11.2017	Germany (Stuttgart)	Juelich
Info Session: Funding Opportunities for Environment & Energy in Horizon 2020	23.11.2017	Belgium (Brussels)	BEA
Oportunidades de financiamento no Desafio Societal Ação Climática para 2018-2020	23.11.2017	Portugal (Aveiro)	FCT
CSIC INHOUSE	23.11.2017	Spain (Madrid)	CDTI
Information Session at University of Johannesburg	23.11.2017	South Africa (Johannesburg)	DST

MADRID INFODAY	24.11.2017	Spain (Madrid)	CDTI
VALENCIA INFODAY	27.11.2017	Spain (Valencia)	CDTI
ECOFIRA	28.11.2017	Spain (Valencia)	CDTI
National Info day Energy	29.11.2017	Slovakia (Bratislava)	CVTI SR
Environment National Infoday	29.11.2017	Italy (Rome)	APRE
Science Forum – Pre Event	06.12.2017	South Africa (Tshwane)	DST
Horizonte 2020 oportunidades de financiamento na temática da economia circular	07.12.2017	Portugal (Porto)	FCT
Infobooth NCPs CaRE at Horizon 2020 health partnering day 2017 (SC1) organised by HNN 2.0	07.12.2017	Belgium (Brussels)	BEA, STIS/BELSP0
Informationsveranstaltung „Fördermöglichkeiten in Horizon2020“	07.12.2017	Germany (Hagen)	Juelich
PL-UK H2020 Brokerage Event on Circular Economy	07.12.2017	Poland (Warsaw)	IPPT
MURCIA INFODAY	11.12.2017	Spain (Murcia)	CDTI
Workshop on SC5 calls in Horizon 2020	12.12.2017	Slovakia (Bratislava)	CVTI SR
CANARIAS INFODAY	14.12.2017	Spain (Las Palmas de Gran Canaria)	CDTI
PAIS VASCO INFODAY	18.12.2017	Spain (Bilbao)	CDTI
CATALUÑA WORKSHOP	18.01.2018	Spain (Barcelona)	CDTI
Informationsveranstaltung Horizon 2020	19.01.2018	Germany (Berlin)	Juelich
Information Session at Central University of Technology	25.01.2018	South Africa (Bloemfontein)	DST
YEAR 4 May	May 2018 – February 2019		
Yearly meeting of the Networks of the European Commission in Slovenia	22.03.2018	Slovenia	MIZŠ
9th national forum of ecoenterprises	29.03.2018	France	ADEME
Workshop - How to write a good proposal?	26.04.2018	France	BELSP0
Brokerage event "Space for climate and smart mobility"	27.04.2018	France	ADEME
Excellence in H2020 project development and proposal writing (UNIDO training course)	17.05.2018	Serbia	EUTA, UNIDO
Financing oportunitis in SC5 H2020	12.06.2018	SPAIN	CDTI
Second Stage proposal preparation	11.07.2018	Spain	CDTI

SC5 2018 infoday - presentation during workshop "Applying for Horizon 2020 funding: hands-on session for cities and regional authorities" with mention of NCPs CaRE	12.09.2018	Belgium	ABAE hub.brussels
Partecipazione Italiana nei temi SC2 e SC5 di Horizon 2020 e prossime opportunità	13.09.2018	Italy	APRE
French Infoday dedicated to Circular Economy calls	25.09.2018	France	ADEME
Conference: Corrosion and surface treatment in industry 2018, VIGLAŠ, Slovakia https://csti.fmmr.tuke.sk/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Leaflet_CSTI_2018.pdf	26.09.2018	Slovakia	CVTI SR
L'economia circolare in Horizon 2020: opportunità di finanziamento	03.10.2018	Italy	APRE
Creative Horizon (Creative Europe - CREA & Horizon 2020 Event)	04.10.2018	Slovenia	MIZŠ
Slovak Info day Days on Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 2 and Societal Challenge 5 – Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials – 2019 calls	17.10.2018	Slovakia, Bratislava	CVTI SR
Financing opportunities in SC5 H2020	17.10.2018	SPAIN	CDTI
Financing opportunities in SC5 H2020	30.10.2018	Spain	CDTI
Financing opportunities in SC5 H2020	05.11.2018	Spain	CDTI
Financing Opportunities in Circular Economy H2020	06.11.2018	Spain	CDTI
Come scrivere una proposta in Horizon 2020. Call 2019	08.11.2018	Italy	APRE
Raw Materials Week 2018	13.11.2018	Belgium	APRE
Financing opportunities in SC5 H2020	13.11.2018	Spain	CDTI
Financing opportunities in SC5 H2020	15.11.2018	Spain	CDTI
Life workshop - funding possibilities for environmental projects	12.12.2018	Slovenia	MIZŠ
Financing opportunities in SC5 H2020	19.12.2018	Spain	CDTI
European Info Day and Brokerage Event - Horizon 2020 Secure Societies 2019	13.03.2019	Belgium	APRE
RURITAGE first workshop	20.03.2019	Spain	APRE
Horizon 2020 info day at Tallinn University of Technology	03.04.2019	Estonia	ETAg
FINANCING OPPORTUNITIES for ECO-INNOVATIONS, organised by Slovak Business Agency	11.04.2019	Slovakia, Bratislava	CVTI SR
Advanced information on international cooperation with specific focus on thematic areas of H2020	15.04.2019	Belgium	Juelich
How to improve collaboration among NCP projects and Partner Country NCPs	16.04.2019	Belgium	Juelich
Horizon 2020 Info day at Estonian University of Life Sciences	17.04.2019	Estonia	Etag
In Deutschland erfolgreich – aber wie geht Europa? (Info day with focus on raw materials, circular economy)	22.-23.05.2019	Germany (Berlin)	Juelich
SC5 Climate topics in 2020 – info event	06.06.2019	Germany (Berlin)	Juelich

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 642025

